

THE CONCEPT OF COUNTERCULTURE AND SUBCULTURE. THEIR MANIFESTATION IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation. Culture is the material and spiritual wealth of an individual or social group. Culture is a hereditary that give information about past. Culture consists of language, processes, lifestyles, customs, values, patterns, and they are reflected in the life of literature art and architecture. The culture of Uzbekistan is unique and vibrant that can be seen in dance, painting, clothing, foods, and traditional music. Culture encompasses the ideas, values, norms, practices and objects that allow a group of people, or even an entire society, to carry out their collective lives with a minimum of friction. We are immersed in a diversity of cultures and subcultures and countercultures are active parts of them. Subcultures include people who may accept much of the dominant culture but are set apart from it by one or more culturally significant characteristic. From the past to the present, Uzbekistan is a multi-ethnic country. Persians, Arabs, Chinese, Russians, Greeks, and nomadic Turkic tribes contributed to the formation of Uzbek culture, which is the epitome of Central Asian culture. It should be noted that today in the territory of Uzbekistan there is a subculture and counterculture, which is one of the types of culture. As you know, digital Countercultures are online communities, and patterns of tech usage, that significantly deviate from mainstream culture. To understand the elements that shape digital countercultures, its best to start with Lingley's classifications of mainstream approaches to digital discourse: that online activity relates to (dis)embodiment, that the Internet is a platform for authenticity and experimentation, and that web-based interactions are placeless. The main difference between subculture and counterculture consists in their relationship with the mainstream culture. The subculture is part of the main culture. Its members mainly choose to stand out by adopting a different image. Although they choose to present themselves differently compared to the rest of the community, they still function and abide by the general rules. By contrast, the members of the counterculture actively go against the mainstream culture. They care less about being visually tied to a group and more about being able to live according to a different set of rules.

Аннотация. Культура – это материальное и духовное богатство отдельного человека или социальной группы. Культура является наследственной, дающей информацию о прошлом. Культура состоит из языка, процессов, образа жизни, обычаев, ценностей, закономерностей, и они отражаются в жизни литературы, искусства и архитектуры. Культура Узбекистана уникальна и ярка, что можно увидеть в танцах, живописи, одежде, еде и традиционной музыке. Культура включает в себя идеи, ценности, нормы, обычаи и объекты, которые позволяют группе людей или даже всему обществу вести свою коллективную жизнь с минимальными трениями. Мы погружены в разнообразие культур, и субкультуры и контркультуры являются их активной частью. Субкультуры включают людей, которые могут принимать большую часть доминирующей культуры, но отличаются от нее одной или несколькими культурно значимыми характеристиками. От прошлого до настоящего Узбекистан – многонациональная страна. Персы, арабы, китайцы, русские, греки и кочевые тюркские племена внесли свой вклад в формирование узбекской культуры, которая является воплощением среднеазиатской культуры. Следует отметить, что сегодня на территории Узбекистана существует субкультура и контркультура, которая является одним из видов культуры. Как вы знаете, цифровые контркультуры — это онлайн-сообщества и модели использования технологий, которые значительно отличаются от основной культуры. Чтобы понять элементы, которые формируют цифровые контркультуры, лучше всего начать с классификаций основных подходов к цифровому дискурсу Лингеля: онлайн-активность связана с (раз)воплощением, что Интернет является платформой для аутентичности и экспериментов, а взаимодействие в Интернете без места.

Основное различие между субкультурой и контркультурой состоит в их взаимосвязи с господствующей культурой. Субкультура - это часть основной культуры. Его члены в основном предпочитают выделяться, принимая другой имидж. Несмотря на то, что они предпочитают представлять себя иначе по сравнению с остальной частью сообщества, они по-прежнему функционируют и соблюдают общие правила.

Напротив, представители контркультуры активно идут против господствующей культуры. Они меньше заботятся о том, чтобы быть визуально привязанными к группе, и больше о том, чтобы иметь возможность жить по другому набору правил.

Key words: A subculture is a small cultural group, A counterculture is the ideology, Oxford English Dictionary determines, counterculture and cultural development.

Introduction. You may have heard these words in discussions about modern society. If you understand what each of them means, then you have noticed that some people use these terms interchangeably, even though this is not the case. If you do not have a firm grasp of the difference between subculture and counterculture, keep reading this article. A subculture is a small cultural group within a larger cultural group. Normally, small communities are more homogeneous, while large communities in big cities tend to favor the creation of numerous forms of subculture. These are usually developed around people with shared interests in music, films, trends and anything that can inspire a lifestyle change. People belonging to these groups will usually make visible changes and adapt their image to make their belonging to the group obvious. The values of the subculture are not altered compared to the values of the mainstream culture. They still function and play a part in society. However, people keep to their own sense of style and their own vocabulary, for example. A counterculture is the ideology of the people going against the mainstream culture. They do not share the same values, and they are actively protesting and trying to change them. The hippie movement and the people protesting the U.S. involvement in the Vietnam War was a good example of opposing sets of values and of people living outside of already established social norms. Being part of a counterculture means having a different set of rules, a different type of behavior and an intentional wish to separate from the unaccepted mainstream values. It implies an active protest against them. According to the Oxford English Dictionary determines subculture, with respect to cultural and sociological, as "an identifiable subgroup within a society or group of individuals, especially one characterized by beliefs or interests at variance with those of the larger group". Subculture is a part of culture that social or individual group. Firstly, subculture an extensive mainstream which can share same trust, daily lifestyle systems or interests. Additionally, the member of subculture have own special clothes and images that anybody cannot repeat it. The research of subculture frequent involves the study of symbolical attached to music, hairstyles, jewelry, and clothing. Example of subculture: punks, hippies, hipsters, goths, and complaints. For instance, Korean Pop "K-Pop" is one of the parts of subculture which is popular among Korean adults. But nowadays it is well known in not only Korea but also the population of whole the world listens it with a high enjoyment. In fact, this kind of subculture contains bandanas, sporty street wear, and hip-hop outfits. The main difference between subculture and counterculture consists in their relationship with the mainstream culture. The subculture is part of the main culture. Its members mainly choose to stand out by adopting a different image. Although they choose to present themselves differently compared to the rest of the community, they still function and abide by the general rules. By contrast, the members of the counterculture actively go against the mainstream culture. They care less about being visually tied to a group and more about being able to live according to a different set of rules. The hippie movement is a good example in both respects. One can be a part of the hippie subculture by merely adopting some visual characteristics such as clothing, eating habits and a general positive attitude. On the other hand, one can become a member of the hippie counterculture and join a community living off grid, grow the food they eat and actively protest everything the system does.

Definition and characteristics of Counterculture. John Milton Yinger originated the term "contra culture" in his 1960 article in American Sociological Review. Yinger suggested the use of

the term contra culture "wherever the normative system of a group contains, as a primary element, a theme of conflict with the values of the total society, where personality variables are directly involved in the development and maintenance of the group's values, and wherever its norms can be understood only by reference to the relationships of the group to a surrounding dominant culture. "Some scholars have attributed the counterculture to Theodore Roszak, author of *The Making of a Counter Culture*. It became prominent in the news media amid the social revolution that swept the Americas, Western Europe, Japan, Australia, and New Zealand during the 1960s. Scholars differ in the characteristics and specificity they attribute to "counterculture". "Mainstream" culture is of course also difficult to define, and in some ways becomes identified and understood through contrast with counterculture. Counterculture might oppose mass culture (or "media culture") or middle-class culture and values. Counterculture is sometimes conceptualized in terms of generational conflict and rejection of older or adult values. Counterculture may or may not be explicitly political. It typically involves criticism or rejection of currently powerful institutions, with accompanying hope for a better life or a new society. It does not look favorably on party politics or authoritarianism. Cultural development can also be affected by way of counterculture. Scholars such as Joanne Martin and Caren Siehl, deem counterculture and cultural development as "a balancing act, [that] some core values of a counterculture should present a direct challenge to the core values of a dominant culture". Therefore, a prevalent culture and a counterculture should coexist in an uneasy symbiosis, holding opposite positions on valuable issues that are essentially important to each of them. According to this theory, a counterculture can contribute a plethora of useful functions for the prevalent culture, such as "articulating the foundations between appropriate and inappropriate behavior and providing a safe haven for the development of innovative ideas". During the late 1960s, hippies became the largest and most visible countercultural group in the United States. According to Sheila Whiteley, "recent developments in sociological theory complicate and problematize theories developed in the 1960s, with digital technology, for example, providing an impetus for new understandings of counterculture". Andy Bennett writes that "despite the theoretical arguments that can be raised against the sociological value of counterculture as a meaningful term for categorizing social action, like subculture, the term lives on as a concept in social and cultural theory... [to] become part of a received, mediated memory". However, "this involved not simply the utopian but also the dystopian and that while festivals such as those held at Monterey and Woodstock might appear to embrace the former, the deaths of such iconic figures as Brian Jones, Jimi Hendrix, Jim Morrison and Janis Joplin, the nihilistic mayhem at Altamont, and the shadowy figure of Charles Manson cast a darker light on its underlying agenda, one that reminds us that 'pathological issues [are] still very much at large in today's world". Counterculture is a culture that gives information about the art, beliefs, and behavior of people who are against to usual or excepted by plenty of society. According to Ken Goffman who is the writer of "Counter culture through the ages" Myth is as important to counter culturalists as historical fact and perhaps more poignant. With a few exceptions (possibly including our current historical moment), countercultures have been inspired, optimistic, one might say mythical historical episodes. Whenever people courageously and passionately engage in rule challenging behaviors that attempt to liberate humans from oppressive limitations (or limitations perceived as being oppressive), excitement, conflict, and scandal - and therefore engaging stories- are sure to follow. There are many exact examples of counterculture in our daily life. For instance, cult religions, criminal gangs, Westbrook Baptist Church, outlaw biker gangs, and 1960's drop- out hippies etc. In fact, 1960's drop-out hippies in USA consist of the Green movement, polygamist, and feminist groups. In details, in 1960, it was rely common problem the war in Vietnam, race relations, women's rights, sexual mores , and traditional modes. The group of hippies was the against to counterculture in the United States. The counterculture also had opportunity to use media in order to represent their concerns to the whole of public. Consequently, it became the reason of serious changes in society. The main examples of subcultures are LGBT, nudists, grunge and bodybuilders. However, countercultures are the groups of individuals who alter in particular ways from dominant culture,

whose norms and values might be inappropriate with it. For example, Romanticism, Suffragettes and Enlightenment. That is to say, a counterculture is inconsistent with opinions, ideas and values of the mainstream culture, whereas a subculture could be consistent with the ideas of the particular definite restriction.

Conclusion. In conclusion, subculture and counterculture are part of the culture that separate people from the society. That is to say, it can be that cause of unusual image among people. As a result, it is widespread in Uzbekistan. Moreover, there is a group of subcultures which is known as a "Punks". This subculture includes a various ideologies, fashion and other types of expression such as, dance, literature and film. There is a common type of punk fashion including T-shirt's, jackets and unusual hairstyles which is painted in bright colors, tattoos, jewelry and body modifications. Punks are also common in USA; however, it has a negative influence in other nations. For example, people around the world are imitating to them. Even, it started to be common in Central Asia. They are mostly imitating by coloring their hair into bright colors, wearing unusual jewelry and putting on strange clothes. Even in Uzbekistan, we can face to these kinds of punk people who imitate them.

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